

Prediction of Preterm Labor Occurrence Using Machine Learning Algorithms

Ms. Josphen Marya Varghese
PG Scholar

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
josphenmaryavarghese@mca.ajce.in

Ms. Anit James
Asst. Professor

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
anitjames@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract: Premature birth is a worldwide public health issue that affects millions of infants per year and causes long-lasting effects. Prediction of premature birth is critical for patient referral to centers capable of treating preterm infants. The outstanding capabilities of machine learning to detect patterns and make predictions have motivated recent studies to improve the prediction of premature birth. However, there is still a high level of uncertainty, especially among patients without a prior premature birth. The objectives of this study were to formulate more effective and accurate predictions of premature birth using machine learning techniques.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Decision Tree, Support Vector Machine, Naïve Bayes

I. INTRODUCTION

Premature birth (delivery before 37 full weeks of pregnancy) is an epidemic that affects nearly 15 million infants annually, according to the WHO. The 10% preterm birth rate in the United States hasn't changed much since the 1980s. Numerous short- and long-term health issues, like as lung illness and delays in neurodevelopment, can affect prematurely born babies. For families and society as a whole, the first intense medical care and ongoing morbidities of preterm infants are expensive.

Inadequate referral and treatment for high level prenatal care are made more difficult by the fact that two thirds of all premature deliveries occur unexpectedly. Short cervix, multiple gestations, in vitro fertilisation, ethnicity, traumatic life events, chronic illnesses like high blood pressure and diabetes, smoking, uterine anomalies, a short inter-pregnancy interval, maternal serum proteins, and a history of spontaneous preterm birth have all been identified as risk factors that affect premature birth. The majority of these research, however, have concentrated on the specific relationships between these risk variables rather than how the whole of life experiences and situations affect risk as they interact and may even amplify one

another.

Recent studies into the prediction of premature delivery have been driven by the growing use of artificial intelligence to find patterns, learn from experience, and make judgments. To forecast the likelihood of premature birth, many algorithms have been fed datasets. These methods provide predictive capacities at various phases of pregnancy and increase prediction accuracy when compared to "purely clinical" efforts.

In this study, we combine machine learning algorithms with clinical assessments of the risk factors for preterm delivery to create more precise and effective forecasts of preterm birth.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

David Cereceda, C. Nataraj, Heather H. Burris, Marc Hershey, and suggested Using clinical data and machine learning to forecast the likelihood of spontaneous preterm births, the study's goals were to create more precise and accurate predictions of sPTB and to pinpoint pertinent risk variables.[1]

The link between prenatal stress and the child birth weight and gestational age at birth was proposed by Wadhwa PD, Sandman CA, Porto M, Dunkel-Schetter C, and Garite TJ: a prospective investigation.[2]

A longitudinal cohort study by Nansel TR, Riggs MA, Yu K-F, Andrews WW, Schwebke JR, and Klebanoff MA put forth the hypothesis that bacterial vaginosis and psychological stress are related. Am J Obstet Gynecol. [3]

Cervicovaginal microbiota and local immune response were suggested by Elovitz MA, Gajer P, Riis V, Brown AG, Humphrys MS, and Holm JB to modify the risk of spontaneous premature delivery. 2019 Nature Comm.[4]

Data mining techniques are suggested by Goodwin LK, Iannacchione MA, Hammond WE, Crockett P, Maher S, and Schlitz K to identify demographic predictors of preterm birth. Nurs Res 2001[5]

III. EXISTING AND PROPOSED SYSTEM

The current system makes an effort to identify the risk factors for preterm or premature birth using a machine learning model based on support vector machines and a radial basis function kernel in order to (i) anticipate the possibility of spontaneous preterm birth and (ii) take into account clinical considerations for treatment.

The suggested system combines Naive Bayes, Decision Trees, and Support Vector Machines to create a Premature Birth Prediction System. The provided dataset is primarily split into two sets: training data and testing data. We are training the model with more data because a dataset with fewer data can't predict the right accuracy rate. The creation of a predicting system is the most important stage in this investigation.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. MACHINE LEARNING

One method of information analysis that takes into account automating the creation of analytical models is machine learning. Artificial intelligence proponents backed the idea that systems will be able to learn from available data, identify patterns, and make decisions with the barest minimum of human input. Modern machine learning has become more effective than it was in its early days thanks to the development of new computing technologies. Since machine learning uses the pattern recognition approach, it is not thought of as being programmed for particular tasks. When given a new set of data, machine learning will be able to forecast how that data will turn out. To get a meaningful result, previous computations are remembered. With the aid of computer science, which focuses on information and algorithms that accurately mimic human learning processes, machine learning might be viewed as the study of computing technology. One of the key fields where machine learning is applied more effectively to forecast the outcomes of data records is regarded to be medicine. Without human involvement, we are able to identify and forecast predictions using machine learning. The method of classifying the data in our dataset that the algorithmic software has learned is known as machine learning classification. Frequently, the options are "Yes" or "No" and either one or zero.

B. MACHINE LEARNING MODELS

i. SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE MODEL

SVMs [8] are effective and adaptable supervised machine learning algorithms used for regression and classification. They are typically applied to categorization issues. Compared to other ML algorithms, SVMs are implemented in a different

method. A SVM model is a multidimensional hyperplane representation of many classes. In order to reduce loss or error, SVM generates the hyperplane in an iterative manner. SVM seeks to maximise the marginal hyperplane by classifying the datasets (MMH).

ii. DECISION TREE CLASSIFIER MODEL

In supervised machine learning, decision tree [6] learning is used. It is comparable to a diagram that people use to depict statistical probabilities or determine the trajectory of an event, an action, or an outcome. The provided concept is made easier to understand by using a decision tree example. A decision tree's branches in a diagram depict a likely result, a potential course of action, and a response. The prediction or outcome is shown on the branch at the decision tree's end. Decision trees are frequently used to tackle problems that become too complex to solve manually. One of the well-liked and effective methods for categorizing and predicting data or an event is the decision tree. It resembles a flowchart but has a tree-like structure. The internal nodes of the trees stand for a test on an attribute; each branch represents a potential result of the test; and the terminal node, also known as the leaf node, represents the test's conclusion.

In a decision tree, we have a number of predictor factors, and we try to anticipate the alleged response variable based on these predictor variables.

iii. NAÏVE BAYES MODEL

A machine learning approach called Naive Bayes[7] is used to address classification issues. The Bayes Theorem served as its foundation. This is one of the most straightforward yet effective machine learning algorithms in use, and it has numerous applications.

Assume you have developed the features and generated the hypothesis for a classification problem you need to answer. To train the dataset, you have a lot of variables and a lot of data points. Use of the Naive Bayes classifier, which is much quicker than other classification algorithms, will be the best course of action in this case.

The Bayes' Theorem is used by naive Bayes, which makes the assumption that each predictor is independent. In other words, it is predicated on the idea that the presence of one specific property in a class does not preclude the existence of another.

The equation for Naive Bayes is as follows:

$$P(C|X) = P(X|C) P(C) / P(X)$$

$$P(C|X) = P(X1 | X) \times P(X2 | C) \times \dots \times P(Xn | C) \times P(C)$$

Here,

- $P(C|X)$ represents the posterior probability for the class(C) given the predictor (X).
- $P(C)$ represents the prior likelihood of the class, and $P(X)$ represents the prior likelihood of the predictor.
- $P(X|C)$ represents the likelihood that the predictor will be present for the given class (C).

C. METHODOLOGY

For the computation of accuracy of the proposed system, the platform used was **Google Colab**.

The dataset file Maternals.xlsx was downloaded from kaggle.com.[9]

The steps we follow are:

1. Importing Dataset and Processing of datasets.
2. Separating data into two groups: training and test.
3. Model Training: SVM Model, Decision Tree Model[6], Naïve Bayes Model[7]
4. Accuracy Evaluation.
5. Building a Predictive System.
6. Accuracy Visualization.

i. DATA PRE-PROCESSING

This is regarded as the beginning of the learning process. In this stage, we clean up our dataset by removing all contaminants and missing values to prepare it for processing. Enhancing the correctness of the data that will be processed is the goal of data pre-processing. The techniques listed below can be used to pre-process data:

1. Removing missing values: A dataset may have some items with missing values, such as 0. These values must be eliminated from the dataset in order to prepare it for quick processing.

2. Splitting the dataset: You must divide the given dataset into a category of Training and Testing sets once the contaminants have been removed. The training set is used to train the model.

ii. INFORMATION GAIN

After preprocessing the dataset, the models have been trained and accuracy is been calculated.

Accuracy calculation in each model is done by **accuracy_score()** method of the sklearn.metrics package

MODEL	TEST ACCURACY	TRAIN ACCURACY
SVM	0.550561797752809	0.5490981963927856

DECISION TREE	0.6067415730337079	0.7915831663326654
NAÏVE BAYES	0.6741573033707865	0.6813627254509018

iii. ACCURACY VISUALISATION

With the help of matplotlib library, accuracy from the models, i.e., Support Vector Machine, Decision tree and Naive Bayes models are compared using bar graph. The graph is shown below:

V. CONCLUSION

The objective of this paper was to prove that the accuracy of prediction using naïve bayes model is higher than that of other models, i.e., decision tree classifier model and support vector machine model.

Accuracy given by Decision Tree Classifier Model[6] is:

Accuracy test: 60.67415730337079
Accuracy train: 79.15831663326654

Accuracy given by Support Vector Machine Model[8] is:

Train Accuracy: 0.5490981963927856
Test Accuracy: 0.550561797752809

Accuracy given by Naïve Bayes Model[7] is:

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↳ Train Accuracy: 0.6813627254509018  
Test Accuracy: 0.6741573033707865
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From the above, it is evident that test accuracy given by naïve bayes model to predict the occurrence of pre-mature birth is higher as compared to the test accuracy given by decision tree classifier model and support vector machine model.

VI. REFERENCE

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